

ANALYSIS OF *GARBHASTHAPANA KSHEERA KASHAYAS*: A CONCEPTUAL
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ABSTRACT

In this ever-dynamic era where abortions are being common, there is an increasing need for medicines which can help in maintaining the pregnancy without leading to any complications. *Ayurveda* plays an important role in this aspect with its time tested *Dravyas* and *Yogas* in *Garbhasthapana* (~Maintenance of pregnancy). Classical references mentioned in *Samhitas* were selected and critical analysis of mode of action of the *Dravyas* were carried out. *Garbhasthapana Dravyas* have an important role in minimising the incidence of abortions and helping in bringing about a healthy pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Abortion, *Ayurveda*, *Garbhasthapana Dravyas*, *Ksheera Kashayas*, Pregnancy.**INTRODUCTION**

The woman is having the unique quality of carrying a life inside her. And in this present Era many are facing difficulties to conceive and even if they conceive, they are having difficulty to carry forward the pregnancy till term. The changed lifestyle, incorrect food habits, working schedule everything becomes a cause for infertility and abortions. In *Ayurveda*, there are various descriptions which highlight the importance of *Ahara* and *Vihara*. These *ahara* only will be acting as medicine when given in the right quantity. *Garbhasthapana Ksheera Kashayas*^[1,2,3] is a set of preparations used for supporting the reproductive health, particularly in women who are preparing for conception, during pregnancy or early stages of pregnancy. It is a part of *Garbhasthapana/ Prajasthapana Gana* aimed at promoting fertility and maintaining a healthy pregnancy. Classical references are available about the *dravyas* which can be used for the purpose of *Garbhasthapana*. Their main action is to prevent abortions and helping in getting a healthy progeny. The four factors which are required for conception are *Ritu*, *Kshetra*, *Ambu* and *Beeja*.^[4] If there is any defect in any of these factors it

hampers the fertility. The *Garbhasthapana Ksheera Kashayas* helps to prevent this by its properties and helps in maintaining the pregnancy. In this paper an attempt is made to study the possible mode of action of some of these *Garbhasthapana Ksheera Kashayas* on helping in maintaining the pregnancies to term and preventing the complications that may arise during the pregnancy period.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To assess the mode of action of *Garbhasthapana Ksheera Kashayas* in preventing abortions and maintaining a healthy pregnancy and promoting the fertility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

References from textbooks like *Ashtanga Hridaya*, *Sahasrayoga*, *Arogya Kalpadruma* regarding the *dravyas* used for *Ksheera Kashayas* for the purpose of *Garbhasthapana* were taken, analysis of probable mode of action of these drugs in preventing abortion and promoting fertility were done.

Garbhasthapana Ksheera Kashayas

The group of drugs mentioned in *Ashtanga Hridaya*¹ in the context of *Garbhasrava*, which are to be

administered month wise, to prevent *Garbhasrava* in a pregnant woman are as described in Table 1.

Table 1: Month wise Ksheera Kashaya according to Ashtanga Hridaya.

Month	Group of Drugs	Botanical Name
1	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
	<i>Saka bija</i>	<i>Tectona grandis</i>
	<i>Payasya</i>	<i>Ipomoea paniculate</i>
	<i>Suradaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>
2	<i>Ashmanthaka</i>	<i>Ficus rumphii</i>
	<i>Krishna Tila</i>	<i>Sesamum indicum</i>
	<i>Tamravalli</i>	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>
	<i>Shatavari</i>	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>
3	<i>Vrikshadani</i>	<i>Dendrophthoe falcate</i>
	<i>Payasya</i>	<i>Ipomoea paniculate</i>
	<i>Latha (Gandha Priyangu)</i>	<i>Callicarpa macrophylla</i>
	<i>Utpala</i>	<i>Nymphaea alba</i>
4	<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidismus indicus</i>
	<i>Ananta</i>	<i>Hemidismus indicus</i>
	<i>Rasna</i>	<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i>
	<i>Padma</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>
	<i>Madhuyashti</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
5	<i>Brihati dvaya</i>	<i>Solanum indicum</i>
	<i>Kashmarya</i>	<i>Gmelina arborea</i>
	<i>Ksheeri shunga tvacha (Nyagrodhadi)</i>	Described in Table 2
6	<i>Prishni parni</i>	<i>Uraria picta</i>
	<i>Bala</i>	<i>Sida cordifolia</i>
	<i>Shigru</i>	<i>Moringa oliefera</i>
	<i>Svadamshtra</i>	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>
	<i>Madhu Parnika</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
7	<i>Sringataka</i>	<i>Trapa bispinosa</i>
	<i>Bhisa</i>	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>
	<i>Draksha</i>	<i>Vitis vinifera</i>
	<i>Kaseru</i>	<i>Scirpus grossus</i>
	<i>Madhuka</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
8	<i>Kapitha</i>	<i>Feronia elephantum</i>
	<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Aegle marmalos</i>
	<i>Brihati</i>	<i>Solanum indicum</i>
	<i>Patola</i>	<i>Tricosanthes dioica</i>
	<i>Ikshu</i>	<i>Saccharum officinarum</i>
	<i>Nidigdihika</i>	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i>
9	<i>Sariva</i>	<i>Hemidismus indicus</i>
	<i>Payasya</i>	<i>Ipomoea paniculate</i>
	<i>Madhu yashti</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
10	<i>Yashti madhu</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>
	<i>Nagara</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>
	<i>Amaradaru</i>	<i>Cedrus deodara</i>

There is description of *Garbhasthapana Ksheera Kashayas* in *Sahasrayogam*^[2] as well as *Arogyakalpadruma*^[3] with slight changes in the month wise drugs mentioned as described in Table 2.

Table 2: Month wise *Ksheera Kashayas*.

Month	Sahasrayoga ^[2]	Arogyakalpadruma ^[3]	Botanical name	
1	Bala	Bala	<i>Sida cordifolia</i>	
2	Lakshmana	Either Lakshmana or Pushkara moola	<i>Ipomoea sepiaria</i>	
3	Brihati	Brihati	<i>Solanum indicum</i>	
		Ksheerivriksha twak	Vata	<i>Ficus bengalensis</i>
			Udumbara	<i>Ficus racemose</i>
			Ashwattha	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>
			Parisha	<i>Ficus lacor</i>
Plaksha	<i>Thespesia populnea</i>			
4	Amshumathi	Amshumathi	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i>	
5	Amrutha	Amrutha	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	
6	Nidigdhika	Nidigdhika	<i>Solanum xanthocarpum</i>	
7	Yavakam	Yavakam	<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	
8	Morata	Morata	<i>Chonemorpha macrophylla</i>	
9	Shatavari	Shatavari	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	
		Jeeraka	<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>	
		Bala	<i>Sida cordifolia</i>	
		Nagara	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	

The month wise administration of the *Ksheera Kashayas* helps in the overall development of the fetus as well as provides strength and nourishment to the pregnant woman. Even *Bala ksheera Kashaya* alone can be given throughout the pregnancy.

DISCUSSION

The drugs described in Table 1 and 2 are analysed for their possible mode of action in preventing abortions. The drug *Yashtimadhu*, is having *Madhura rasa* and *Sheeta virya*. *Yashtimadhu* is described in the management of *Shushka Garbha*.^[5] It can be used for treating conditions like Intra Uterine Growth Retardation also. In an animal study conducted to examine the effect of Glycyrrhiza glabra extract (GgE) on the fertilization and embryonic development in vitro, there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in the fertilization rate of SUO mice oocytes (53.89%) by using 10% GgE Compared to IVF medium alone in SUO group (36.82%).^[6] It is also having property of inhibiting Chromosomal aberrations.^[7]

Saka bija contains proteins which helps in improving the endometrial thickness, thereby improving the chances of conception and implantation of the fertilized embryo.^[8] *Payasya* is having *madhura rasa*, *sheeta virya* and it possess *guru*, *snigdha guna*, thereby it helps in *Pushti*, *bala vardhana* and does *vayasthapana*.^[9] *Suradaru* is having *Tikta rasa* and *ushna virya* unlike other drugs advised in the first month of pregnancy. It is having *laghu*, *snigdha gunas*.^[10] It contains active principles like Matairesinol, Nortrachelogenin, and dibenzylbutyro lactollignan which are having anti-oxidant property; thus, it may serve in preventing *garbhasrava* in the first month of pregnancy.^[11] The drug *Ashmanthaka* is having *Kashaya rasa*, *Sheeta Virya* and *Laghu, Ruksha Guna*.^[12] It is antimicrobial so it helps in preventing any infections from occurring or helps in controlling the infections already present.

Krishna tila is a good source of B- Complex Vitamins such as folic acid. The usage may help in reduction of chances of neural tube defect in the foetus.^[13] *Tamravalli* is the synonym of *Manjishtha*, and is having *Rakta shodhaka* (~Blood purifier) property. In an Animal study conducted^[14] it was shown to inhibit the aggregation of Platelets in the Rabbits platelets. It may help in improving the circulation to the foetus and also nourishes the *garbhashaya* and prevents abortions. *Shatavari*, as found from animal studies, helps in preventing the uterine contractions^[15] and as such helps in preventing abortions from occurring. The drugs like *Lata*, *Utpala*, *Sariva*, *Padma* helps in balancing the *Rakta* and *Pitta*. Thereby preventing any kind of abortions. The drug *Rasna*^[16] which is *agrya* in preventing *Vata* vitiation, plays a pivotal role in preventing abortions. Also prevents *Vata* vitiation in the pregnant lady. The drugs *Bruhati*, *Ksheerivriksha*, *Kashmarya* described in the 5th month of pregnancy have properties like *shotha hara*^[17], and is described in the management of *Shushka Garbha*.^[18] The drugs in the 6th month are having properties of reducing oedema and is *nutruala* in nature, which helps in preventing the formation of Pedal oedema which are common in Pregnancy. The drugs *Shringataka*, *Bisa*, *Draksha*, etc mentioned in the 7th month have properties like immunomodulation, *garbhashthapana*.^[19] The drugs mentioned in the last three months are mainly *Bruhmaniya*, *Jivaniya* in action which gives the nourishment to both fetus as well as the mother.

When coming to the *Ksheera kashayas* described in *Sahasrayogam* and *Arogyakalpadruma*, there we can see *Bala*, *Lakshmana*, *Guduchi*, *Jeeraka*, *Nagara* which are not described in the *Ashtanga Hridaya* in the context of month wise *Kashayas*. The drug *Bala* has properties which will help in keeping a check over the water retention, anti-bacterial, anti-diabetic in nature.^[20] *Lakshmana* is described in the context of

Pumsavana^[21], which in turn will do the *Garbhasthapana* action. *Guduchi* is having *Balya*, *Rasayana*, *Medhya*^[22] which will help in the overall development of the foetus. *Nidigdika* is having anti-inflammatory action, mentioned in *Shothahara maha Kashaya*.^[23] *Yavaka ksheera Kashaya* is mentioned to be taken in the seventh month of pregnancy and it is having properties like *Ojo vardhana*, *Balya*, and *Dhatu poshana* which helps in the maternal as well as fetal wellbeing.^[24] *Jeeraka* and *Nagara* are told in the ninth month of pregnancy, both the drugs are having *Vata anulomana* property which is required for a normal labour to occur. It is also having *Dipana*, *Pachana* properties.^[25]

All these medicines are given in the form of *Ksheera Kashaya* and thus *Ksheera* plays as an integral part in this. It is having *Madhura rasa*^[26] and it helps the drugs to be more palatable. It is having properties like *Jeevaniya*^[27], *Balya* and congenial to the pregnancy state.

CONCLUSION

The month wise *Ksheera Kashayas* mentioned in the classical textbooks have mainly *Madhura rasa*, *Tiktha*, *Kashaya rasa* properties. This in turn are having action like *Sthambhana*, *Sheeta Virya*, *Brumhana* property. When we critically analyse the properties of each drug, it is understood that these preparations not only help in preventing abortions or promoting a healthy pregnancy, but also helps in improving the vitality of the pregnant woman.

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REFERENCES

- Vagbhata, Ashtanga Hridaya, Srikantha Murthy K R, Krishnadas Academy, Varanasi. 5th Ed, 2001; Pg no. 389-390.
- KV Krishnan Vaidya, S Gopala Pillai. Sahasrayogam, Sujanapriya commentary, 30th ed, Vidyarambham Publishers: Alappuzha, 2011; p.104.
- Syamala B. Kaikulangarayude Arogyakalpadrumam. Ch.39/Parishtachikitsa Prakarana 29-32, Samrat Publishers: Thrissur, 495.
- Ambikaduttashastri K. Susruta Samhita of Susruta, Sharirasthana; Shukra Shonita shuddhi Shareeram adhyaya Chapter 2, Verse 35. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Samsthana, 19.
- Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, With Ayurveda Deepika Commentary by Chakrapanidatta, Edited by Yadavji Trikamji, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Reprint 2016, Chikitsa sthana 28th chapter, Verse 95, Page no 621.
- Saad SA, Alaa SA. Effect of Glycyrrhiza glabra extract on IVF outcome in Mice: Experimental model for mammals. Biotechnology Research Center (special edition), 2009; 3(2).
- Sharma V, Agarwal RC. Evaluation of anticlastogenic effects of Glycyrrhiza glabra root extract against Cyclophosphamide induced chromosomal aberration in Swiss albino mice. Journal of applied pharmaceutical science, 2015; 5(06): 127-132.
- Vyas P, Yadav DK, Khandelwal P. Tectona grandis (teak)—A review on its phytochemical and therapeutic potential. Natural product research, 2019 Aug 18; 33(16): 2338-54.
- Shri Bhavamishra, Bhavaprakash Nighantu, edited by Pandit Ramtej Pandeya, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratisthan, Reprint 2016, Guduchyadivarga, Page no 131.
- Bapalal G. Vaidya, Nighantu Adarsh, Chaukhamba Bharati Academy, Reprint 2013, Uttarardha (Part 2), Page no. 541.
- Chaudhary, A. K., Ahmad, S., & Mazumder, A. (2011). Cedrus deodara (Roxb.) Loud.: a review on its ethnobotany, phytochemical and pharmacological profile. Pharmacognosy Journal, 3(23): 12-17.
- Bapalal G. Vaidya, Nighantu Adarsh, Chaukhamba Bharati Academy, Reprint 2013, Purvardha (Part 1), Page no. 492.
- Biswas, S., Natta, S., Ray, D. P., Mondal, P., & Saha, U. (2018). Til (Sesamum indicum L.)—An underexploited but promising Oilseed with multifarious applications: A Review. International Journal of Bioresource Science, 5(2): 127-139
- Patil Rupali, Mohan Mahalaxmi, Kasture Veena, Kasture Sanjay: Rubia cordifolia: a review. Oriental Pharmacy and Experimental Medicine, 2009; 9(1): 1-13.
- Pandey SK et al, Effect of Asparagus racemosus rhizome (Shatavri) on mammary gland and genital organs of pregnant rat. PhytotherRes, 2005; 19(8): 721-724.
- Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita Ayurveda Dipika Commentary by Chakrapanidatta, edited by Vaidya Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan, Varanasi, Reprinted – 2011, Sutra Sthana 25th chapter, Verse- 40, Pp-738, 637.
- Hameed IH, Cotos MR, Hadi MY. A review: Solanum nigrum L. antimicrobial, antioxidant properties, hepatoprotective effects and analysis of bioactive natural compounds. Research Journal of Pharmacy and Technology, 2017 Nov 1; 10(11): 4063-8.
- Munira, B., Gururaja, G. M., Deepak, M., Roopashree, T. S., & Shashidhara, S. (2013). An overview on phytochemistry and pharmacological properties of Gmelina arborea. Journal of Natural Product and Plant Resources, 3(4): 62-71.
- Ahmed, H., Hakani, G., Aslam, M., & Khatian, N. (2019). A review of the important pharmacological activities of Nelumbo nucifera: A prodigious rhizome. International Journal of Biomedical and Advance Research, 10(01): e5007.
- Singh A. Ethnobotanical, Pharmacological Benefits and Phytochemistry of Sida cordifolia (Linn.): A Review. International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research, 2018 Jan 18; 10(01): 16-21.

21. Tiwari PV, Kasyapa Samhita, English translation, Choukambha Visvabharathi: Varanasi, 2008; p.665.
22. Sharma PV, Sharma GP. "Kaiyadeva Nighantu". Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2006; p. 5.
23. Vanya Gupta, Om Prakash Gupta. Exploring the Medicinal Importance of Kantakari: A review. J Ayurveda Integr Med Sci, 2003; 04:194-206.
24. Agnivesha, Charaka Samhita, Ayurveda Deepika commentary by Chakrapanidatta, Edited by Yadavji Trikamji Acharya, Sutrasthana; Atreyabhadrakapiyam adhyaya: Chapter 26, Verse 43(1). Varanasi: Chaukhambha Prakashana, 2011; pg. 144.
25. Sastry JLN; Dravyaguna vijnana; Vol 2; Chakambha Orientalia, Varanasi; Reprint edition, 2016; Pg 519.
26. Shastri K, Charaka Samhita of Charaka with Vidyotini Hindi Commentary, Sharirasthana, Reprint ed; 2013. Chapter 27, verse 218-19. Chaukhambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2019.
27. Satyapala B, Vidyotini Hindi Commentary Kasyapa Samhita, Khilasthana 22/10, Chaukambha Sanskrit Sansthan, 2019; Pp- 545.